

Akashiwo sanguinea blooms, anoxia and mass mortality of fish and invertebrates during the 2023–2024 spring–summer “El Niño” in Peru

Fig. 1. (A). Distribution of *Akashiwo sanguinea* (cells · mL⁻¹) in Peruvian coastal water. (B–C). Remote sensing detection of the discolorations. Remote sensing (IOPifa, MODIS- AQUA) satellite detection of the bloom. (D). Callao - Station 1. February - April 2024.

In early 2023, the advection of warm equatorial surface waters to the Peruvian coast, with positive anomalies of 6–8°C in sea surface temperature (SST) (related to the 1991–2020 mean, [1]), signalled the onset of the Western Pacific 2023–2024 El Niño Southern Oscillation (ENSO) event. In February–March 2024, still under the influence of a moderate-to-weak El Niño (El Niño Coastal Index – ICEN), a bloom of *Akashiwo sanguinea* (K.Hirasaka) Gert Hansen & Moestrup 2000 developed. Dark brown discolorations visible to the naked eye and extending along 1,272 km of coastline (04°S to 14°S), persisted for 2 months (February to early April 2024) and caused mass mortalities of marine fauna and heavy losses to the shellfish industry (Fig. 1). This event was monitored by personnel from the Instituto del Mar del Perú (IMARPE) and other regional laboratories.

Akashiwo sanguinea is a cosmopolitan dinoflagellate widely distributed in coastal waters, including the Humboldt Current Upwelling System, where it causes major socioeconomic impacts [2, 3]. Since the 1980s, recur-

ring summer and autumn blooms of *A. sanguinea* have become the most frequent high-biomass HAB in the region. The duration of these blooms has progressively increased from a few days to weeks, and in some cases, up to 3 months, as seen in summer 1986 [4], 2004 [3], and 2017 [5].

In 2024, surface water samples were collected from various geograph-

ic locations exhibiting discolorations. Additional sampling was conducted at a fixed station in Miraflores Bay, Callao (12°S). There, CTD (0–15 m) casts measured physical properties and water column structure, while water samples were collected with Niskin bottles at 0 m, 5 m, 10 m and 15 m for chemical and microphytoplankton analyses. Cell counts were carried out using 1-mL Sedgewick-Rafter chambers.

Maximal cell densities of *Akashiwo sanguinea* (ranging from 1.3×10^6 to 63×10^6 cells L⁻¹) and Chl *a* concentrations up to 241.7 µg L⁻¹ were recorded within the top 5 m, corresponding to a SST range of 19.4°–27.3 °C and sea surface salinity (SSS) between 34.32–35.39. Vertical profiles of environmental conditions (Fig. 2) revealed moderate-to-low levels of inorganic nutrients in the top 10 m layer and anoxic conditions from 10 to 15 m, with dissolved oxygen (DO) depleting at 10 m. Compared to abiotic conditions during similar events (SST: 18°–25°C; SSS: 34.372–35.224) from 2000 and 2018, the 2024 event occurred within a broader temperature (+2°C) and salinity (+0.1) range (Fig. 3).

A. sanguinea is a constitutive mixotroph, with a capacity to perform photosynthesis with its own plastids in addition to feed on live prey. *Akashiwo* benefits from different inorganic and organic nitrogen sources (including ni-

Fig. 2. Temperature–Salinity (T-S) diagram during *Akashiwo sanguinea* (2000–2018) events.

Fig. 3. (A). Vertical distribution of cell densities (cells·mL⁻¹) of *Akashiwo sanguinea* and accompanying phytoplankton groups. (B). Temperature, salinity and Chl a. (C). Nutrients and dissolved oxygen levels in March 2024.

trate, ammonia, and urea) and eat cyanobacteria and nanoflagellates. This nutritional versatility allows the species to persist and proliferate for extended periods when resources are limiting for other competitors [6].

To estimate the extent and spatio-temporal dynamics of the discolorations, remote sensing monitoring utilised a satellite index (IOPifa) generated with daily high-resolution satellite data on phytoplankton absorption (aphy, GIOP) and non-algal detrital material plus coloured dissolved organic matter, CDOM (adCDOM, GIOP) from the Generalized Inherent Optical Properties (GIOP) model of MODIS-Aqua [7]. Despite cloudy weather, the estimated IOPifa index exceeded 2, indicating a good physiological status (fitness) of the offshore *A. sanguinea* populations. Discolourations extended offshore, ranging from about 4 km off Punta La Negra to 43 km off Pisco (Fig. 1 A, B).

During the last week of March, local

fishermen reported mass mortalities of marine fauna in Balneario San Bartolo - Lima (12°25'00"S) and Paracas Bay - Pisco (13°49'20,5"S), leading to significant economic losses over an area equivalent to 900 m². Various marine fish and invertebrate species were washed ashore (Table 1) under SSTs of 27.4 °C, a pH of 7.3, and depleted oxygen levels. Anoxia was particularly harmful to the "concha abanico" (Peruvian calico scallop, *Argopecten purpuratus*), the primary commercially exploited species in the region. Losses exceeded USD 12 million in Paracas Bay when SST ranged from 22.3 to 26.5 °C and DO levels ranged from 0.71 to 3.80 mL L⁻¹. Values below 1 mL L⁻¹ were measured in the areas where mass mortalities were reported.

Mass mortality of invertebrates and fish may have been triggered by a combination of gill clogging and oxygen depletion during bloom decay. However, the precise mechanism of fish mortality caused by *Akashiwo* remains

unknown. Laboratory culture experiments have shown that *A. sanguinea*'s toxicity changes across population growth phases. Lithic substances, which are lethal to zooplankton and inhibit the growth of other phytoplankton species, were most prominent during the exponential to declining growth phases [8]. Mucilage and resting cyst formation observed towards the end of the blooms may indicate unfavourable conditions or the conclusion of the growth season [9].

Observations during the 2024 *A. sanguinea* bloom in Peru suggest populations displayed good physiological fitness and tolerance to broader than usual temperature ranges. Future blooms are likely, even in a climate change scenario, as the species appears resilient to increased temperature, acidification or irradiance [10].

Increased duration and geographic extent of recurring *A. sanguinea* blooms in Peruvian coastal waters will exacerbate their negative impacts on artisanal fisheries and shellfish resources. Supporting ongoing monitoring activities is crucial. Enhanced research is needed to i) identify the drivers and origins of these blooms and ii) unveil the mechanisms underlying the intense and long-lasting blooms in the Humboldt Upwelling system, Peru.

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Table 1. List of fish and invertebrate taxa included in the mass mortality of marine fauna.

Sample type	Scientific Name	Common names Spanish	Common names English - FAO
Fish	<i>Eucinostomus sp.</i>	Mojarra	Pacific flagfin mojarra
	<i>Fistularia corneta</i>	Pez corneta	Pacific cornetfish
	<i>Gymnura marmorata</i>	Raya mariposa	California butterfly ray
	<i>Mugil cephalus</i>	Lisa	Flathead grey mullet
	<i>Paralichthys adspersus</i>	Lenguado	Fine flounder
	<i>Pseudobatos planiceps</i>	Guitarra	Pacific guitarfish
	<i>Scomber japonicus</i>	Caballa	Pacific chub mackerel
	<i>Scartichthys gigas</i>	Borracho	Giant blenny
	<i>Stellifer minor</i>	Mojarrilla	Minor stardrum
Invertebrate	<i>Argopecten purpuratus</i>	Concha de abanico	Peruvian calico scallop
	<i>Farfantepenaeus californiensis</i>	Langostino café	Yellowleg shrimp
	<i>Octopus mimus</i>	Pulpo	Head-footed octopus
	<i>Pattalus mollis</i>	Pepino de mar	Sea cucumber
	<i>Platyanthus orbigny</i>	Cangrejo violáceo	Crab

Fig. 4. Mass mortality of fan shell from Paracas Bay – Pisco (13°49'20,5" S), March 2024.

<https://diariocorreo.pe/edicion/ica/pisco-maricultores-de-la-zona-de-atenas-denuncian-mortandad-de-conchas-de-abanico-noticia/>

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Fig. 5. Different species of marine organisms washed on the beaches (March 2024).